

LEVEL OF WORK EFFICIENCY OF SCHOOL HEALTH PROGRAM ADMINISTRATORS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF OPLAN KALUSUGAN IN SCHOOLS DIVISION OF TARLAC PROVINCE: BASIS FOR POLICYMAKING

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated the effectiveness of school health program administrators in executing the *Oplan Kalusugan* (OK) initiatives, focusing on five key result areas (KRAs): strategic leadership, operational and resource management, prioritization of teaching and learning, personal and professional development, and the cultivation of relationships. Employing a quantitative descriptive correlational design, data were collected from 100 administrators through a structured questionnaire. The analysis revealed considerable variation in work efficiency across all KRAs, indicating a range from Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. Few cases showed significant relationships between administrators' work efficiency and demographic characteristics such as age, gender, years of service, and educational attainment. Key challenges identified include insufficient funding, delays, inefficient procurement, and inadequate training. Recommendations emphasize targeted interventions to enhance leadership, management, teaching, professional development, and stakeholder engagement. Addressing these issues through increased financial support, streamlined processes, and improved training is essential for effective program implementation. The study provides a basis for developing policies to improve the efficiency of school health program administrators, ultimately enhancing student health and wellbeing in Tarlac Province. Future research should employ mixed methods and larger samples to further explore factors influencing work efficiency.

Keywords: *School health program administrators, school health programs, oplan kalusugan, work efficiency, key result areas, policy development*

INTRODUCTION

School health programs (SHPs) are vital for students' well-being, promoting healthy lifestyles, and enhancing academic performance. Governments play a crucial role in fostering health-promoting schools and involving the community in health initiatives. Despite recognition, SHP implementation varies, facing challenges from basic needs to promoting healthy lifestyles.

Effective SHPs require stakeholder involvement and rely on administrators. In their absence, teachers often assume these roles, as seen in Myanmar, improving health knowledge and behaviors despite resource constraints. Studies in Nigeria by Gyasi et al. (2023) highlighted challenges like poor coordination and lack of resources, yet SHPs positively impact health and academics.

Teachers experience significant workloads, which contribute to burnout and affect their performance. Research by Jomuad et al. (2021) and Zydziunaite et al. (2020) indicates that, despite experiencing high levels of fatigue, teachers maintain strong performance. The implementation of SHPs, a form of teacher leadership, has been shown to enhance motivation and efficiency. Factors such as organizational habits and burnout play a role in determining work efficiency (Baldikov, 2024). Antin (2018) corroborates these findings in the context of Sabah, Malaysia.

School administrators are key in promoting student well-being and integrating health initiatives. In the Philippines, the *Oplan Kalusugan* (OK sa DepEd) program relies on administrators. Despite their importance, studies on their work efficiency and demographics are limited. In Tarlac Province, many administrators are also teachers, showing commitment to student well-being despite multiple roles.

Moreover, the Key Result Areas (KRAs) are essential for assessing the effectiveness of school health program administrators (SHPAs), including principals and school heads, in implementing SHPs. These KRAs, as detailed in DepEd Order No. 024, s. of 2020, known as the "National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads," provide a comprehensive framework. This framework aligns strategic leadership, resource and operations management, teaching and learning, personal and community development, and the establishment of connections with the broader educational system's goals. Evaluating performance in these areas allows for an assessment of SHP implementation effectiveness and highlights areas needing improvement (Department of Education, 2020).

There are several studies that highlight the complexities of implementing school health programs (SHPs). Dalisay et al. (2024) emphasized cross-sector collaboration and public-private partnerships to improve the WASH in Schools (WinS) program, addressing challenges like deworming hesitancy, funding, and access to remote areas.

Mationg et al. (2023) examined the cost-effectiveness of the "Magic Glasses Philippines" health package, showing that hiring teachers for mass drug administration (MDA) significantly reduces expenses while enhancing program efficiency.

Ashipala and Shapopi (2022) analyzed factors influencing health service delivery in Namibia, such as participant understanding, service delivery challenges, and remedial strategies.

Ninkron et al. (2021) in Thailand highlighted the role of drug availability and family dynamics in substance abuse, emphasizing the need for comprehensive community-based interventions.

Darlington et al. (2018) underscored the importance of contextual factors, such as leadership and school climate, in the success of health promotion programs. Together, these studies provide valuable insights into enhancing SHP implementation across diverse contexts.

Research shows that demographic factors such as age, experience, and gender significantly influence the efficiency of school health program administrators (SHPAs). Lin et al. (2024) noted that older professionals, who report higher job satisfaction, tend to exhibit greater efficiency, while Guzzo et al. (2022) found tenure, rather than age alone, to be a key predictor of performance.

Ogasawara et al. (2021) and Rivera (2018) highlighted the impact of gender, showing that female administrators often excel due to empathetic communication and organizational skills.

Pricellas et al. (2016) demonstrated that experienced administrators in the Philippines are better leaders, emphasizing the importance of both age and experience in effective administration.

Rivera (2019) confirmed these findings in Tarlac Province, showing that experienced personnel enhance program execution. Global perspectives, such as Levinson et al. (2019), reinforce that experience and expert knowledge are critical to efficient health service delivery. These findings underscore the importance of tenure, gender diversity, and job satisfaction in enhancing SHP administration.

Strategic leadership and resource management are essential for the work efficiency of SHPAs. Barola and Digo (2022) found no significant correlation between demographic characteristics and strategic leadership performance but emphasized its importance in educational leadership.

Carvalho et al. (2021) identified gaps in integrating strategic leadership concepts into SHP implementation, calling for further research. Samimi et al. (2020) highlighted key characteristics of strategic leaders, such as vision, influence, and adaptability, linking these to organizational outcomes.

Studies on resource management, including Hernandez (2024) and Silva and Andal (2023), revealed strong connections between effective governance and improved school performance, highlighting the importance of budgeting, auditing, and professional development.

Valenzuela and Buenvenida (2021) noted that competencies in operations management significantly enhance program success. Eyana et al. (2024) examined challenges faced by school heads, including resource limitations and curriculum demands, advocating for strategic planning to overcome these issues. These studies collectively emphasize the need for strategic leadership, resource management, and professional growth to improve SHPA efficiency.

The aforementioned studies highlight that the implementation of school health programs is a complex task, heavily reliant on the capabilities of program administrators. This complexity led the researcher to explore the available information regarding the work efficiency of school health program administrators in the Schools Division of Tarlac Province. The primary objective was to determine how the efficiency of these administrators significantly impacts the effectiveness of school health programs, such as *OK sa DepEd* initiatives. Given the challenges in implementing these programs, this study aimed to assess the productivity of SHPAs in the Schools Division of Tarlac Province and examine how their demographic characteristics influence their work efficiency. Additionally, the study sought to identify the specific problems these SHPAs faced in performing their responsibilities and provided valuable insights into areas that may require targeted support and intervention.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to assess the work efficiency of the school health program administrators in implementing *OK sa DepEd* programs in the Schools Division of Tarlac Province, and specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions.

1. How are the respondents be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Gender;
 - 1.3. Years of Service; and
 - 1.4. Highest Educational Attainment.
2. How are the level of work efficiency of the respondents be described with reference to:
 - 2.1. Leading strategically;
 - 2.2. Managing school operations and resources;
 - 2.3. Focusing on teaching and learning;
 - 2.4. Developing self and others;
 - 2.5. Building connection.
3. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and work efficiency of school health program administrators?
4. What are the problems encountered in the implementation of the *OK (Oplan Kalusugan)* sa Department of Education programs among the respondents?

5. What intervention measures could be proposed to address the identified problems in the implementation of *Oplan Kalusugan* programs?
6. What are the implications of the study to the quality of implementation of OK sa DepEd programs in the Schools Division of Tarlac Province?

Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the demographic profile and work efficiency of school health program administrators.

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in the Schools Division of Tarlac Province, located in the Central Luzon region of the Philippines. This division encompasses a total of 511 public schools, including Central Elementary Schools, Elementary Schools, and Secondary Schools. From these, 100 SHPAs were randomly selected to participate in the study. These administrators, comprising principals and head teachers, accepted their roles during the academic year 2023-2024. The Schools Division of Tarlac Province is organized into 33 districts, each managed by a team of 36 School Nurses who oversee the implementation of health programs across the schools.

Sampling Design and Participants

The study involved public school SHPAs from the Schools Division of Tarlac Province, Central Luzon, Philippines. These SHPAs, including principals and head teachers who accepted their roles during the academic year 2023-2024, were randomly selected from various school levels to yield more varied data and ensure diverse results. Using a random sampling method, 100 SHPAs were selected from 51 public schools, and informed consent was obtained. Moreover, confidentiality measures were implemented to protect participants' information.

Table 1
Respondents of the study

Participants	Frequency (<i>f</i>)
Elementary Central School Principals	33
Elementary School Head Teachers	17
Secondary School Principals	25
Secondary School Head Teachers	25
Total	100

Data Gathering Procedure

The research procedure commenced with the submission of a formal request to the Superintendent of the Schools Division of Tarlac Province, seeking approval to

conduct a survey using a questionnaire specifically intended for school health program administrators. Upon obtaining approval, collaborative efforts with the Division School Health Unit were initiated, engaging the thirty-six (36) School Nurses. Dissemination of the survey questionnaire link was requested within their respective districts, and this was done through established group chat channels.

Prior to survey distribution, respondents were given detailed information about the study's goal, and they received assurances about the confidentiality of any contributed information. Following the survey phase, the researcher meticulously organized and encoded the acquired data, ensuring orderly management and preparation for future study. This rigorous and methodical methodology aimed to maintain ethical standards, secure essential clearances, and expedite data collection for future researchers to replicate.

Research Instrument

Data was gathered using a standardized questionnaire created by the researcher after a thorough review process. It was based on an Origines (2022) study that identified key competencies for effective school management, which were divided into Key Result Areas (KRAs): Leading Strategically, Managing School Operations and Resources, Focusing on Teaching and Learning, Developing Self and Others, and Building Connections. These KRAs were translated into concrete items related to the tasks of school health program administrators in implementing *Oplan Kalusugan's* flagship programs.

The face validity of the questionnaire was evaluated by three experts: a grammarian, a statistician, and a coordinator. They used Simon and White's Survey/Interview Validation Rubric (VREP©), which yielded a mean score of 4.0, indicating Exceeds Expectations.

Reliability testing with 30 respondents revealed Cronbach's Alpha values ranging from 0.803 to 0.957, indicating high reliability. According to Taber (2018), values above 0.70 are acceptable, and those above 0.90 are excellent. The highest reliability was observed in Adolescent Reproductive Health and Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services under KRA 4 (Developing Self & Others), with a value of 0.957. Even the lowest value of 0.803 for Water, Sanitation & Hygiene in Schools under KRA 1 fell within the "Good" range.

After reliability testing, a pilot test with 30 respondents further refined the questionnaire. The survey, administered online via Google Forms, collected demographic information and measured work efficiency using a 5-Point Likert Scale ranging from Highly Efficient (5), Efficient (4), Neither Efficient nor Inefficient (3), Inefficient (2), to Highly Inefficient (1). It also identified problems encountered by administrators in performing tasks.

Table 2
Level of Work Efficiency

Scale	Mean Range	Description	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Always	Highly Efficient	Tasks are consistently completed promptly and with exceptional outcomes, showcasing exemplary time management skills.
4	3.41-4.20	Often	Efficient	Tasks are generally completed on time and with satisfactory outcomes, demonstrating effective time management.
3	2.61-3.40	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient	Time management and task completion are average, with occasional delays or missed deadlines.
2	1.81-2.60	Rarely	Inefficient	Time management and task completion are often compromised, resulting in delays or subpar outcomes.
1	1.00-1.80	Never	Highly Inefficient	Tasks are consistently delayed or incomplete due to poor time management or inefficiencies.

Data Analysis

Following the data collection process, the researcher calculated the respondents' demographic profile using frequency counts and percentages. The mean, a measure of central tendency, was used to calculate the average work efficiency of SHPAs. It was computed by dividing the sum of all values by the total number of values. Understanding the dataset's variability and distribution is crucial for comprehensive descriptive statistical analysis (Bhandari, 2023).

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was employed to evaluate the relationship between the demographic profile of the SHPAs and their work efficiency. This coefficient is a descriptive statistic that summarizes the characteristics of a dataset, indicating the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two quantitative variables (Turney, 2024).

The challenges faced by the respondents were then prioritized to determine further factors influencing the implementation of SHPs within the division.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study aimed to examine the relationship between the demographic characteristics and work efficiency of school health program administrators in the Schools Division of Tarlac Province in 2024. It excluded non-teaching staff and teachers classified as Teacher I to Teacher III. The focus was on those transitioning from teaching roles to leadership positions in accordance with DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2024, also known as the “Immediate Removal of Administrative Tasks of Public School Teachers.”

Research exclusions included elements outside of the designated time range and geographic limits outside of the Schools Division of Tarlac Province.

RESULTS

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 3
Distribution of the respondents according to age

Age Range	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
30-35	21	21%
36-41	15	15%
42-47	26	26%
48-53	18	18%
54-59	18	18%
60-65	2	2%
Total	100	100.00

Table 3 shows how responses were distributed according on age. The youngest responders are 30 years old, while the oldest are 60. The highest frequency of 26 occurs between the ages of 42-47, accounting for 26% of the sample. Furthermore, the 60-65 age group has the lowest frequency, accounting for only 2% of respondents with a frequency of two (2).

Table 4
Distribution of the respondents according to gender

Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	53	53.00
Female	47	47.00
Total	100	100.00

Table 4 shows that the gender distribution reveals a slight predominance of male respondents, with 53 individuals (53%) identifying as male. Moreover, 47 individuals (47%) identifying as female.

Table 5
Distribution of the respondents according to years of service

Years of Service	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
10-15	20	20.00
16-21	24	24.00
22-27	18	18.00
28-33	17	17.00
34-39	21	21.00
40-45	20	20.00
Total	100	100

Table 5 shows the distribution of the respondents according to years of service. The data revealed that the highest frequencies are observed in the 34-39 years, encompassing a frequency of 21, comprising 21% of the respondents. Moreover, the shortest years of service is eight under the range 28-33, with a frequency of 17, comprising 17% of the respondents.

Table 6
Distribution of the respondents according to highest educational attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Master's Degree	25	25.00
Doctorate Degree	75	75.00
Total	100	100.00

Table 6 shows the distribution of respondents' highest educational attainment levels. The majority of responders, 75 (75.00%), have earned a doctorate degree. A large number of the responders, 25 (25.00%), hold a Master's Degree.

Level of Work Efficiency

Table 7

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of WASH in Schools under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically

WASH in Schools	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Handwashing facilities are installed and kept fully operational as planned.	3.37	1.34	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
2. Regular water quality tests for handwashing stations are conducted as scheduled.	3.08	1.35	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. Advocacy for deworming, promoting holistic health and nutrition with a target reach of 85% of learners, is facilitated to ensure comprehensive student well-being.	2.91	1.35	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. The availability and maintenance of the water supply for drinking and handwashing are consistently monitored and ensured.	2.58	1.15	Rarely	Inefficient
5. A systematic approach to managing the cleanliness and maintenance of sanitation facilities is implemented effectively.	1.94	1.25	Rarely	Inefficient
Grand Mean	2.78	1.29	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 7 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of WASH in schools under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically. The grand mean is 2.78 which has description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is under the task “Handwashing facilities are installed and kept fully operational as planned.” with a mean of 3.37 which has description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. On the other hand, the lowest level of work efficiency is under the task “A systematic approach to managing the cleanliness and maintenance of sanitation facilities is implemented effectively.” with a mean of 1.94 which has description of Rarely and a descriptive rating of Inefficient.

Table 8

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of School-Based Feeding Program under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically

School-Based Feeding Program	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Coordination with suppliers and kitchen staff effectively ensures timely meal preparation and service.	3.65	1.45	Often	Efficient
2. Food safety standards are regularly met during the preparation and service of meals.	3.64	1.49	Often	Efficient
3. Daily meal logs and reports are consistently completed and submitted on time.	3.43	1.64	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Meal distribution is reliably managed within the designated time frame each day.	3.20	1.25	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Food procurement and delivery are consistently completed according to the established schedule.	2.75	1.56	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.33	1.48	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 8 displays the respondents' level of work efficiency during the implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically. The grand mean is 3.33, with a description of "Sometimes" and a descriptive rating of neither efficient nor inefficient. The task "Coordination with suppliers and kitchen staff effectively ensures timely meal preparation and service." has the highest level of work efficiency, with a mean of 3.65 and a descriptive rating of Efficient. On the other hand, the task described as "Food procurement and delivery are consistently completed according to the established schedule." has the lowest level of work efficiency,

with a mean of 2.75, a description of Sometimes, and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 9
Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of National Drug Education Program under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically

National Drug Education Program	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Educational sessions are effectively delivered with documented participant engagement.	3.66	1.40	Often	Efficient
2. Any issues related to material delivery or program implementation are promptly resolved.	3.39	1.61	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. Records of material distribution and program attendance are accurately maintained.	3.38	1.58	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Availability of drug education materials is ensured in all designated locations.	3.14	1.73	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Distribution of drug education materials is consistently conducted according to the established schedule.	3.09	1.31	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.33	1.53	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 9 depicts the respondents' level of work efficiency in the implementation of the National Drug Education Program under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically. The grand mean is 3.33, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is under the task “Educational sessions are effectively delivered with documented participant engagement.” with a mean of 3.66, which has a description of Often and a

descriptive rating of Efficient. On the other hand, the lowest level of work efficiency is under the task “Distribution of drug education materials is consistently conducted according to the established schedule.” with a mean of 3.09, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 10
Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically

Adolescent Reproductive Health	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Distribution of educational materials on reproductive health is consistently executed according to the established schedule.	3.72	1.36	Often	Efficient
2. Reproductive health education materials are reviewed regularly to ensure they are comprehensive and reflect current information.	3.50	1.28	Often	Efficient
3. Advocacies on adolescent reproductive health and teenage pregnancy, including comprehensive sexuality education, are facilitated to provide holistic support for learners' well-being and development.	3.34	1.28	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Documentation and analysis of participation in reproductive health programs are regularly conducted to assess effectiveness.	3.19	1.45	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Technology is utilized to manage and streamline data related to reproductive health education effectively.	2.48	1.16	Rarely	Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.25	1.31	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 10 displays the respondents' level of work efficiency when implementing the Adolescent Reproductive Health program under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically. The grand mean is 3.25, which has a description of Sometimes and a

descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is under the task “Distribution of educational materials on reproductive health is consistently executed according to the established schedule.” with a mean of 3.72, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. On the other hand, the lowest level of work efficiency is under the task “Technology is utilized to manage and streamline data related to reproductive health education effectively.” with a mean of 2.48, which has a description of Rarely and a descriptive rating of Inefficient.

Table 11
Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Mental Health under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically

Mental Health	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Accurate documentation of mental health interventions and follow-ups is consistently maintained to ensure effective support for learners.	3.39	1.49	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
2. Regular training and resources are provided to staff to ensure effective mental health support for learners.	3.06	1.27	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. Mental health advocacies, including the provision of psychosocial support services, the facilitation of mental health awareness campaigns, and the integration of mental health education into lessons, are actively supervised and implemented.	2.66	1.24	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Technology is utilized to manage and analyze data related to mental health services effectively.	2.46	1.11	Rarely	Inefficient
5. Issues related to the implementation of mental health programs are addressed swiftly to minimize disruption to learner support services.	2.39	1.31	Rarely	Inefficient
Grand Mean	2.79	1.28	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 11 displays the respondents' level of work efficiency during the implementation of the Mental Health program under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically. The grand mean is 2.79, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is under the task "Accurate documentation of mental health interventions and follow-ups is consistently maintained to ensure effective support for learners." with a mean of 3.39, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. On the other hand, the lowest level of work efficiency is under the task "Issues related to the implementation of mental health programs are addressed swiftly to minimize disruption to learner support services." with a mean of 2.39, which has a description of Rarely and a descriptive rating of Inefficient.

Table 12

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically

Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Health records are consistently maintained with a high level of accuracy and confidentiality to protect learner information.	3.98	1.04	Often	Efficient
2. Resources, including MOOE funds and donations, are efficiently managed for the procurement of essential items like health kits, medicines, clinic supplies, toothbrushes, toothpaste, and soap, in compliance with established policies to ensure the success of school health initiatives.	3.33	1.30	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. Effective utilization of technology is managed to analyze health service data, enabling informed decision-making and enhancing learner outcomes.	3.05	1.71	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Regular evaluations of health services are facilitated to identify areas for continuous improvement in student care.	2.78	1.28	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. School personnel training on health services is provided regularly to ensure that care aligns with the DepEd vision and mission.	2.37	0.98	Rarely	Inefficient

Grand Mean	3.10	1.26	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
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Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 12 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically. The grand mean is 3.10, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is under the task “Health records are consistently maintained with a high level of accuracy and confidentiality to protect learner information.” with a mean of 3.98, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. On the other hand, the lowest level of work efficiency is under the task “School personnel training on health services is provided regularly to ensure that care aligns with the DepEd vision and mission.” with a mean of 2.37, which has a description of Rarely and a descriptive rating of Inefficient.

Table 13

Summary of the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically

Summary of KRA 1: Leading strategically	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. School-Based Feeding Program	3.33	1.48	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
2. National Drug Education Program	3.33	1.53	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. Adolescent Reproductive Health	3.25	1.31	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services	3.10	1.26	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Mental Health	2.79	1.28	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
6. WASH in Schools	2.78	1.29	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.10	1.36	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: $SD < 1.0$ = low variability, SD between $1.0 - 1.25$ = moderate variability, $SD > 1.25$ = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 13 summarizes the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs under Key Result Area (KRA) 1: Leading Strategically. The grand mean is 3.10, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed in both the School-Based Feeding Program and the National Drug Education Program, each with a mean of 3.33, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is found in the WASH in Schools program, with a mean of 2.78, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 14

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of WASH in Schools under Key Result Area (KRA)2: Managing School Operations & Resources

WASH in Schools	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. The availability and maintenance of water supply for drinking and handwashing are consistently monitored to ensure adherence to established schedules.	3.49	1.23	Often	Efficient
2. Handwashing facilities are consistently installed and maintained to meet operational standards and are fully functional for student use.	3.45	1.68	Often	Efficient
3. Waste management practices are regularly evaluated to ensure a clean and safe school environment that meets the needs of all learners.	3.11	1.16	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. The cleanliness and regular maintenance of sanitation facilities are effectively managed to optimize resource utilization and operational efficiency.	3.02	1.33	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Regular testing of water quality in school facilities is supervised, ensuring that results are properly documented and promptly addressed to meet safety standards.	2.18	1.30	Rarely	Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.05	1.34	Sometimes	Neither Efficient

**nor
Inefficient**

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 14 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of WASH in Schools under Key Result Area (KRA) 2: Managing School Operations & Resources. The grand mean is 3.05, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is under the task “The availability and maintenance of water supply for drinking and handwashing are consistently monitored to ensure adherence to established schedules.” with a mean of 3.49, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. On the other hand, the lowest level of work efficiency is under the task “Regular testing of water quality in school facilities is supervised, ensuring that results are properly documented and promptly addressed to meet safety standards.” with a mean of 2.18, which has a description of Rarely and a descriptive rating of Inefficient.

Table 15

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of School-Based Feeding Program under Key Result Area (KRA)2: Managing School Operations & Resources

School-Based Feeding Program	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Completion of all required documentation for food distribution, including daily logs and reports, is managed and evaluated accurately and submitted punctually.	4.39	0.99	Always	Highly Efficient
2. Meal distribution is systematically managed to occur within the designated time frame each day.	3.96	1.06	Often	Efficient
3. Coordination between suppliers and kitchen staff is facilitated to ensure prompt meal preparation and service.	3.46	1.33	Often	Efficient
4. Food procurement and delivery processes are managed according to the established schedule.	3.11	1.30	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Food safety standards are upheld during meal preparation to ensure the health and safety of learners.	3.06	1.51	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.60	1.24	Often	Efficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 15 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program under Key Result Area (KRA) 2: Managing School Operations & Resources. The grand mean is 3.60, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. The highest level of work efficiency is under the task “Completion of all required documentation for food distribution, including daily logs and reports, is managed and evaluated accurately and submitted punctually.” with a mean of 4.39, which has a description of Always and a descriptive rating of Highly Efficient. On the other hand, the lowest level of work efficiency is under the task “Food safety standards are upheld during meal preparation to ensure the health and safety of learners.” with a mean of 3.06, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 16

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of National Drug Education Program under Key Result Area (KRA)2: Managing School Operations & Resources

National Drug Education Program	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Availability of drug education materials in all designated locations is supervised.	3.86	1.03	Often	Efficient
2. Prompt resolution of issues related to the delivery of mental health education materials or the implementation of mental health programs is effectively managed.	3.14	1.59	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. Educational sessions on drug prevention are supervised effectively, with participant engagement documented for future reference.	3.08	1.32	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Carrying out of the distribution of drug education materials is managed according to the planned schedule.	2.57	1.57	Rarely	Inefficient
5. Maintenance and updating of records of material distribution and attendance at drug education programs is supervised.	2.35	1.18	Rarely	Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.00	1.34	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 16 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of the National Drug Education Program under Key Result Area (KRA) 2: Managing School Operations & Resources. The grand mean is 3.00, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is under the task “Availability of drug education materials in all designated locations is supervised.” with a mean of 3.86, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. On the other hand, the lowest level of work efficiency is under the task “Maintenance and updating off records of material distribution and attendance at drug education programs is supervised.” with a mean of 2.35, which has a description of Rarely and a descriptive rating of Inefficient.

Table 17

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health under Key Result Area (KRA)2: Managing School Operations & Resources

Adolescent Reproductive Health	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. The collection of feedback from participants in reproductive health programs is supervised and utilized to enhance future sessions.	3.21	1.30	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
2. The distribution of educational materials on reproductive health is managed according to the established schedule.	3.06	1.35	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. The review and updating of reproductive health education materials are supervised to ensure comprehensiveness and relevance.	2.90	1.55	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. The maintenance of documentation regarding participation in reproductive health programs is accurately supervised and analyzed for continuous improvement.	2.79	1.37	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Training for facilitators of reproductive health programs is regularly supervised to ensure high-quality delivery of content.	2.66	1.63	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	2.92	1.44	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: $SD < 1.0$ = low variability, SD between $1.0 - 1.25$ = moderate variability, $SD > 1.25$ = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 17 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health under Key Result Area (KRA) 2: Managing School Operations & Resources. The grand mean is 2.92, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is under the task “The collection of feedback from participants in reproductive health programs is supervised and utilized to enhance future sessions.” with a mean of 3.21, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. On the other hand, the lowest level of work efficiency is under the task “Training for facilitators of reproductive health programs is regularly supervised to ensure high-quality delivery of content.” with a mean of 2.66, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 18
Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Mental Health under Key Result Area (KRA)2: Managing School Operations & Resources

Mental Health	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. The collection of feedback from mental health workshops and counseling sessions is managed and analyzed to enhance program effectiveness.	3.90	1.22	Often	Efficient
2. The evaluation of mental health awareness initiatives is monitored for their effectiveness and relevance to learners' needs.	3.52	1.37	Often	Efficient
3. The provision of counseling services for mental health concerns is supervised to ensure there are no delays.	3.35	1.45	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. The implementation of support programs for mental health, following the established plan and timelines, is supervised.	3.22	1.24	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. The integration of school-based mental health programs into classroom activities, as per the planned schedule, is supervised.	2.72	1.28	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.34	1.31	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: $SD < 1.0$ = low variability, SD between $1.0 - 1.25$ = moderate variability, $SD > 1.25$ = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 18 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Mental Health under Key Result Area (KRA) 2: Managing School Operations & Resources. The grand mean is 3.34, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is under the task “The collection of feedback from mental health workshops and counseling sessions is managed and analyzed to enhance program effectiveness.” with a mean of 3.90, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. On the other hand, the lowest level of work efficiency is under the task “The integration of school-based mental health programs into classroom activities, as per the planned schedule, is supervised.” with a mean of 2.72, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 19

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services under Key Result Area (KRA)2: Managing School Operations & Resources

Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. The reviewing and updating of emergency medical protocols to ensure learner safety is supervised.	4.00	1.14	Often	Efficient
2. The evaluation of access to medical, dental, and nursing services is supervised to ensure it meets the diverse needs of all learners.	3.21	1.31	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. The maintenance of health records and documentation is managed with high accuracy and confidentiality.	3.01	1.52	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. The establishment of policies and guidelines on health service delivery is supervised to ensure quality and efficiency.	2.75	1.33	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. The evaluation of health services is managed to identify areas for continuous improvement.	2.16	1.25	Rarely	Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.03	1.31	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: $SD < 1.0$ = low variability, SD between $1.0 - 1.25$ = moderate variability, $SD > 1.25$ = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 19 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services under Key Result Area (KRA) 2: Managing School Operations & Resources. The grand mean is 3.03, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is under the task “The reviewing and updating of emergency medical protocols to ensure learner safety is supervised.” with a mean of 4.00, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. On the other hand, the lowest level of work efficiency is under the task “The evaluation of health services is managed to identify areas for continuous improvement.” with a mean of 2.16, which has a description of Rarely and a descriptive rating of Inefficient.

Table 20

Summary of the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs under Key Result Area (KRA)2: Managing School Operations & Resources

Summary of KRA 2: Managing school operations and resources	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. School-Based Feeding Program	3.60	1.24	Often	Efficient
2. Mental Health	3.34	1.31	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. WASH in Schools	3.05	1.34	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services	3.03	1.31	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. National Drug Education Program	3.00	1.34	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
6. Adolescent Reproductive Health	2.92	1.44	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.16	1.33	Sometimes	Neither Efficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 20 summarizes the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs under Key Result Area (KRA) 2: Managing School Operations & Resources. The grand mean is 3.16, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed in the School-Based Feeding Program with a mean of 3.60, which has a description Often and descriptive rating of Efficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is found in the Adolescent Reproductive Health program, with a mean of 2.92, which has a description Sometimes and descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 21

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of WASH in Schools under Key Result Area (KRA)3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning

WASH in Schools	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Supervision of the evaluation of cleanliness and functionality of sanitation facilities is conducted to ensure they meet established standards.	3.52	1.52	Often	Efficient
2. Collection of feedback from learners and school personnel is managed to improve hygiene and sanitation programs in the school.	3.47	1.42	Often	Efficient
3. Delivery of hygiene education sessions is supervised according to the planned health education periods.	3.41	1.12	Often	Efficient
4. Assessment and adjustments of the overall effectiveness of hygiene and sanitation programs are facilitated based on the collected results for continuous improvement.	3.06	1.40	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Supervised handwashing activities are managed during designated times to ensure full participation of all learners.	2.70	1.81	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Grand Mean

3.23

1.45

Sometimes

**Neither
Efficient
nor
Inefficient**

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 21 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of WASH in Schools under the Key Result Area (KRA)3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning. The grand mean is 3.23 and has a description of Sometimes with a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest work level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Supervision of the evaluation of cleanliness and functionality of sanitation facilities is conducted to ensure they meet established standards.” with a mean 3.52 which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Supervised handwashing activities are managed during designated times to ensure full participation of all learners.” which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 22

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of School-based Feeding Program under Key Result Area (KRA)3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning

School-Based Feeding Program	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. The provision of the school-based feeding program and the dissemination of information on healthy eating practices and the importance of nutrition in promoting the overall well-being of learners are supervised.	3.90	0.98	Often	Efficient
2. Conducting nutritional assessments is managed to inform the preparation of meals for the feeding program.	3.45	1.40	Often	Efficient
3. The overall effectiveness of the feeding program is evaluated, and adjustments are made to ensure that student nutritional needs are met.	3.21	1.38	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Technical assistance is provided to school teaching personnel and canteen staff in managing the feeding program to ensure it	3.19	1.35	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

aligns with health and learning objectives.				
5. Collection of learner feedback on meal quality, including presentation and taste, is facilitated and considered for program improvements.	2.54	1.11	Rarely	Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.26	1.24	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 22 depicts the respondents' level of work efficiency in implementing the School-Based Feeding Program under Key Result Area (KRA) 3: Focusing on Teaching and Learning. The grand mean is 3.26, and the descriptive rating is Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task "The provision of the school-based feeding program and the dissemination of information on healthy eating practices and the importance of nutrition in promoting the overall well-being of learners are supervised." with a mean of 3.90, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task "Collection of learner feedback on meal quality, including presentation and taste, is facilitated and considered for program improvements." with a mean of 2.54, which has a description of Rarely and a descriptive rating of Inefficient.

Table 23

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of National Drug Education Program under Key Result Area (KRA)3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning

National Drug Education Program	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Drug education programs that create meaningful learning experiences contributing to improved learner attitudes toward drug prevention are facilitated.	3.72	1.35	Often	Efficient
2. Learner participation in drug education seminars is consistently monitored and documented.	3.67	1.25	Often	Efficient
3. Collection of learners' feedback on drug prevention sessions is managed and used to enhance the program's effectiveness.	3.59	1.26	Often	Efficient
4. Conducting drug prevention seminars and activities is	3.24	1.26	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

facilitated in line with the established school calendar.				
5. The review of drug education materials for clarity and relevance is supervised to ensure that key messages are effectively communicated.	3.09	1.22	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.46	1.27	Often	Efficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 23 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of the National Drug Education Program under Key Result Area (KRA) 3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning. The grand mean is 3.46 and has a description of Often with a descriptive rating of Efficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Drug education programs that create meaningful learning experiences contributing to improved learner attitudes toward drug prevention are facilitated.” with a mean of 3.72, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “The review of drug education materials for clarity and relevance is supervised to ensure that key messages are effectively communicated.” with a mean of 3.09, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 24
Level of work efficiency of the respondents the implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health under Key Result Area (KRA)3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning

Adolescent Reproductive Health	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Workshops on reproductive health are facilitated to be engaging and well-received by learners.	3.32	1.31	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
2. The effectiveness of reproductive health programs is regularly reviewed, with interventions implemented based on assessment outcomes.	2.83	1.41	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. Management of reproductive health counseling sessions are consistently held and tailored to meet learners' individual needs.	2.56	1.07	Rarely	Inefficient
4. Reproductive health education sessions are supervised in alignment with the school's scheduled learning plans.	2.37	1.39	Rarely	Inefficient
5. Collection of feedback from learners on reproductive health	2.23	1.56	Rarely	Inefficient

sessions is supervised and used to improve program delivery.

Grand Mean	2.66	1.35	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
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Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 24 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health under Key Result Area (KRA) 3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning. The grand mean is 2.66 and has a description of Sometimes with a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Workshops on reproductive health are facilitated to be engaging and well-received by learners.” with a mean of 3.32, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Collection of feedback from learners on reproductive health sessions is supervised and used to improve program delivery.” with a mean of 2.23, which has a description of Rarely and a descriptive rating of Inefficient.

Table 25

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Mental Health under Key Result Area (KRA)3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning

Mental Health	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Collection of feedback from learners on mental health support services is supervised and used to improve future programs.	3.47	1.29	Often	Efficient
2. Mental health counseling sessions are scheduled and implemented in accordance with the school's learning plans.	3.16	1.20	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. Professional delivery of mental health counseling services is supervised and aligned with best practices, ensuring positive learner experiences.	3.13	1.60	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Mental health programs are reviewed and adapted based on student learning outcomes to enhance their effectiveness.	3.02	1.55	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. The integration of mental health programs into the school environment is supervised to	2.96	1.24	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

provide a safe and supportive space for learners.

Grand Mean	3.15	1.38	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
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Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 25 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Mental Health under Key Result Area (KRA) 3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning. The grand mean is 3.15 and has a description of Sometimes with a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Collection of feedback from learners on mental health support services is supervised and used to improve future programs.” with a mean of 3.47, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “The integration of mental health programs into the school environment is supervised to provide a safe and supportive space for learners.” with a mean of 2.96, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 26

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services under Key Result Area (KRA)3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning

Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Medical, dental, and nursing services are collaborated in accordance with professional standards, ensuring that learner health needs are met efficiently.	3.84	1.35	Often	Efficient
2. The school environment is managed to support a healthy and inclusive atmosphere, ensuring the timely delivery of nursing and emergency care.	3.56	1.17	Often	Efficient
3. Supervision of routine medical check-ups and health assessments is facilitated and coordinated according to the scheduled health program, integrating them into learner activities.	3.43	1.24	Often	Efficient
4. Health services, including dental care, are consistently reviewed and adapted based on student	3.39	1.60	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

health outcomes to ensure continuous improvement.				
5. Collection of feedback from learners and parents on medical and dental services is supervised and used to improve the quality of health care.	2.83	1.52	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.41	1.38	Often	Efficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 26 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services under Key Result Area (KRA) 3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning. The grand mean is 3.41 and has a description of Often with a descriptive rating of Efficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Medical, dental, and nursing services are collaborated in accordance with professional standards, ensuring that learner health needs are met efficiently.” with a mean of 3.84, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Collection of feedback from learners and parents on medical and dental services is supervised and used to improve the quality of health care.” with a mean of 2.83, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 27

Summary of the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs under Key Result Area (KRA)3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning

Summary of KRA 3: Focusing on teaching and learning	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. National Drug Education Program	3.46	1.27	Often	Efficient
2. Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services	3.41	1.38	Often	Efficient
3. School-Based Feeding Program	3.26	1.24	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. WASH in Schools	3.23	1.45	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Mental Health	3.15	1.38	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
6. Adolescent Reproductive Health	2.66	1.35	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.20	1.34	Sometimes	Neither Efficient

**nor
Inefficient**

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 27 shows the summary of the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of OK sa DepEd programs under the Key Result Area (KRA)3: Focusing on Teaching & Learning with a grand mean 3.20 which has a description of Sometimes and descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency can be observed on the National Drug Education Program with a mean 3.46 which has a description Often and descriptive rating Efficient. Moreover, the lowest level of work efficiency can be observed under the program of Adolescent and Reproductive Health with a mean 2.66 which has a description Sometimes and descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 28

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of WASH in Schools under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self and Others

WASH in Schools	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. The technical working group is assigned leadership roles in supervising the timely restocking of handwashing facilities with soap and water.	3.70	1.18	Often	Efficient
2. Opportunities are regularly provided for the technical working group to lead the monitoring and maintenance of water supply and handwashing facilities.	3.55	1.53	Often	Efficient
3. Acknowledgment is given to stakeholders who consistently contribute to maintaining high standards of sanitation and water safety within the school.	3.48	1.47	Often	Efficient
4. Professional development sessions are conducted to enhance the skills of the technical working group in managing sanitation facilities and ensuring water quality.	3.22	1.48	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. The efforts of stakeholders who actively participate in maintaining and improving sanitation and handwashing facilities are	2.23	1.36	Rarely	Inefficient

highlighted during school meetings or events.

Grand Mean	3.24	1.40	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
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Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 28 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of WASH in Schools under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self and Others with a grand mean of 3.24 which has a description of Sometimes and descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “The technical working group is assigned leadership roles in supervising the timely restocking of handwashing facilities with soap and water.” with a mean 3.70 which has a description Often and descriptive rating Efficient. Moreover, the lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “The efforts of stakeholders who actively participate in maintaining and improving sanitation and handwashing facilities are highlighted during school meetings or events.” with a mean 2.23, description of Rarely and descriptive rating Inefficient.

Table 29

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of School-Based Feeding Program under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self and Others

School-Based Feeding Program	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Training on food safety standards is provided to staff as part of their professional development in the feeding program.	3.99	1.22	Often	Efficient
2. Teams responsible for meal distribution are given opportunities to showcase leadership in managing daily operations and addressing challenges.	3.21	1.60	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. School teaching personnel involved in the feeding program regularly receive training to enhance their food handling skills and address any performance gaps.	3.00	1.60	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

4. Staff recognition for exemplary performance in managing the feeding program is consistently provided to motivate continued excellence.	2.68	1.70	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Opportunities for kitchen staff and food service teams to take on leadership roles within the feeding program are provided regularly.	2.64	1.22	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.10	1.47	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 29 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of School-Based Feeding Program under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self and Others with a grand mean 3.10 which has a description Sometimes and descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Training on food safety standards is provided to staff as part of their professional development in the feeding program.” with mean 3.99 which has a description Often and a descriptive rating Efficient. Moreover, the lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Opportunities for kitchen staff and food service teams to take on leadership roles within the feeding program are provided regularly.” with a mean 2.64 which has a description Sometimes and descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 30

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of National Drug Education Program under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self and Others

National Drug Education Program	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Opportunities are provided for teachers and staff to take leadership roles in organizing and leading drug prevention education programs.	3.60	1.15	Often	Efficient
2. Professional development initiatives related to drug education are incorporated during learning action cell (LAC) sessions to enhance staff capabilities and address areas for improvement.	3.20	1.38	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

3. The technical working group is regularly recognized for its contributions to the successful implementation of the drug education program.	3.13	1.42	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Feedback on the effectiveness of the drug education program is used to identify professional development needs and improve staff performance.	2.80	1.65	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Team collaboration in delivering drug education sessions is encouraged and acknowledged as part of leadership development.	2.36	1.37	Rarely	Inefficient

Grand Mean	3.02	1.39	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
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Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 30 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of National Drug Education Program under Key Result Area (KRA) 4: Developing Self and Others with a grand mean 3.01 which has a description Sometimes and a descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Opportunities are provided for teachers and staff to take leadership roles in organizing and leading drug prevention education programs.” With a mean score of 3.60 which has a description Often and descriptive rating Efficient. Moreover, the lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Team collaboration in delivering drug education sessions is encouraged and acknowledged as part of leadership development.” with a mean score of 2.36 which has a description Rarely and descriptive rating Inefficient.

Table 31

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self and Others

Adolescent Reproductive Health	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Professional development sessions on adolescent reproductive health are regularly provided to enhance the knowledge and skills of school personnel.	3.58	1.40	Often	Efficient
2. Opportunities are offered for teachers and members of the technical working group to lead reproductive health programs, encouraging leadership development.	3.38	1.38	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. Teachers and members of the technical working group are acknowledged for effectively addressing and resolving reproductive health issues among learners.	3.34	1.49	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Teachers and members of the technical working group on adolescent reproductive health education programs are encouraged to take leadership roles in program delivery and improvement.	3.24	1.40	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Recognition is given to stakeholders who demonstrate exceptional contributions in implementing adolescent reproductive health initiatives.	2.72	1.25	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.25	1.38	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 31 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self and Others with a grand mean 3.25 which has a description Sometimes and descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency

is observed under the task “Professional development sessions on adolescent reproductive health are regularly provided to enhance the knowledge and skills of school personnel.” with a mean score of 3.58 which has a description Often and descriptive rating Efficient. Moreover, the lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Recognition is given to stakeholders who demonstrate exceptional contributions in implementing adolescent reproductive health initiatives.” with a mean score 2.72 which has a description Sometimes and descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 32

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Mental Health under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self and Others

Mental Health	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Opportunities are provided for stakeholders and teachers to showcase their mental health initiatives, with recognition for those that make a significant impact.	3.76	1.26	Often	Efficient
2. Professional development programs on mental health are regularly conducted to enhance the skills and knowledge of school personnel.	3.45	1.46	Often	Efficient
3. Opportunities are provided for teaching personnel responsible for mental health support programs to take on leadership roles in designing and improving these initiatives.	3.34	1.36	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Stakeholders and teaching personnel are recognized and rewarded for their exceptional contributions to the school’s mental health programs.	3.03	1.61	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Opportunities for school personnel to lead mental health initiatives and programs are offered to foster leadership development.	2.65	1.33	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.25	1.40	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: $SD < 1.0$ = low variability, SD between $1.0 - 1.25$ = moderate variability, $SD > 1.25$ = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 32 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Mental Health under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self and Others with a grand mean 3.25 which has a description Sometimes and descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Opportunities are provided for stakeholders and teachers to showcase their mental health initiatives, with recognition for those that make a significant impact.” with a mean score of 3.76 which has a description Often and descriptive rating Efficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Opportunities for school personnel to lead mental health initiatives and programs are offered to foster leadership development.” with a mean score of 2.65 which has a description Sometimes and descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 33

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self and Others

Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Stakeholders and school personnel involved in health programs are acknowledged for providing timely and effective medical and dental services to learners.	3.94	1.13	Often	Efficient
2. Collaborative workshops and peer-learning sessions are organized to empower teaching personnel in improving the quality and management of health and nutrition for learners.	3.57	1.34	Often	Efficient
3. Professional development sessions addressing performance gaps in the delivery of school health services are regularly conducted.	3.16	1.38	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Training and mentorship are provided to teaching personnel to enhance their skills in leading and managing medical, dental, and nursing services within the school.	3.06	1.69	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Stakeholders and personnel are given opportunities for professional growth through leadership roles in the	2.19	1.45	Rarely	Inefficient

implementation of health and nutrition-related programs.

Grand Total	3.18	1.40	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
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Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 33 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self and Others with a grand mean 3.18 which has a description Sometimes and descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Stakeholders and school personnel involved in health programs are acknowledged for providing timely and effective medical and dental services to learners.” with a mean score of 3.94 equivalent to the description Often and a descriptive rating Efficient. Moreover, the lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Stakeholders and personnel are given opportunities for professional growth through leadership roles in the implementation of health and nutrition-related programs.” with a mean score of 2.19 which has a description Sometimes and a descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 34

Summary of level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self & Others

Summary of KRA 4: Developing Self and Others	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Adolescent Reproductive Health	3.25	1.38	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
2. Mental Health	3.25	1.40	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. WASH in Schools	3.24	1.40	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

4. Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services	3.18	1.40	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. School-Based Feeding Program	3.10	1.24	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
6. National Drug Education Program	3.02	1.39	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.17	1.37	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 34 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs under Key Result Area (KRA)4: Developing Self & Others with a grand mean 3.17 which has a description Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the program Adolescent Reproductive Health with a mean score of 3.25 which has a description Sometimes and a descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. Moreover, the lowest level of work efficiency is observed under National Drug Education Program with a mean score of 3.02 which has a description Sometimes and a descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 35

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of WASH in Schools under Key Result Area (KRA)5: Building Connection

WASH in Schools	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Partnerships with local health authorities are established to promote clean water and sanitation initiatives within the school.	4.19	1.10	Often	Efficient
2. School organizations collaborate with the school to support the implementation of WASH programs for learners.	3.62	1.24	Often	Efficient

3. Local industries and stakeholders provide resources and assistance to improve water and sanitation infrastructure at the school.	3.58	1.58	Often	Efficient
4. Community members and parents actively participate in maintaining hygiene and sanitation facilities at the school.	3.53	1.45	Often	Efficient
5. The school regularly engages with community leaders to strengthen efforts in promoting hygiene awareness among learners.	2.84	1.50	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.55	1.37	Often	Efficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 35 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of WASH in Schools under Key Result Area (KRA) 5: Building Connection. The grand mean is 3.55 and has a description of Often with a descriptive rating of Efficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Partnerships with local health authorities are established to promote clean water and sanitation initiatives within the school.” with a mean of 4.19, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “The school regularly engages with community leaders to strengthen efforts in promoting hygiene awareness among learners.” with a mean of 2.84, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 36

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of School-Based Feeding Program under Key Result Area (KRA)5: Building Connection

School-Based Feeding Program	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Local businesses and industries provide food donations or resources to support the School-Based Feeding Program.	3.32	1.48	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
2. Parents regularly volunteer to assist in the preparation and distribution of meals for the School-Based Feeding Program.	3.23	1.52	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. School organizations collaborate with the school to enhance the nutritional content of the meals provided in the feeding program.	2.97	1.24	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

4. The school partners with local health authorities to monitor and improve the nutritional outcomes of learners in the feeding program.	2.45	1.38	Rarely	Inefficient
5. Community leaders are engaged to raise awareness and gather support for the sustainability of the School-Based Feeding Program.	2.38	1.46	Rarely	Inefficient

Grand Mean	2.87	1.42	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
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Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 36 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program under Key Result Area (KRA) 5: Building Connection. The grand mean is 2.87 and has a description of Sometimes with a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Local businesses and industries provide food donations or resources to support the School-Based Feeding Program.” with a mean of 3.32, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Community leaders are engaged to raise awareness and gather support for the sustainability of the School-Based Feeding Program.” with a mean of 2.38, which has a description of Rarely and a descriptive rating of Inefficient.

Table 37

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of National Drug Education Program under Key Result Area (KRA)5: Building Connection

National Drug Education Program	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Law enforcement and community leaders engage with the school to co-facilitate drug awareness sessions for both learners and parents.	3.23	1.46	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
2. School organizations regularly participate in mentoring programs to share experiences and promote drug-free lifestyles among learners.	3.06	1.18	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

3. Local businesses and industries collaborate with the school to provide resources or sponsorship for drug education initiatives.	3.02	1.36	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Parents and community members actively participate in organizing and supporting drug prevention seminars and activities for learners.	2.85	0.90	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Partnerships with local health authorities and organizations are established to enhance drug education campaigns in the school.	2.59	1.33	Rarely	Inefficient

Grand Mean	2.95	1.25	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
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Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 37 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of the National Drug Education program under the Key Result Area (KRA) 5: Building Connections, and the grand mean is 2.95 and has a description of Sometimes with a descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Law enforcement and community leaders engage with the school to-cofacilitate drug awareness sessions for both learners and parents,” and this has a mean of 3.23, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Partnerships with local health authorities and organizations are established to enhance drug education campaigns in the school.” with a mean of 2.59, which has a description of Rarely and a descriptive rating of Inefficient.

Table 38

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health under Key Result Area (KRA)5: Building Connection

Adolescent Reproductive Health	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Collaborative activities with parents and stakeholders are conducted to raise awareness of adolescent reproductive health.	3.19	1.61	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

2. Parents and community leaders are actively involved in planning and executing adolescent reproductive health initiatives.	3.07	0.92	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. The school coordinates with health professionals to provide workshops on reproductive health for learners and their families.	2.91	1.32	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. The school partners with local health authorities to ensure the timely delivery of adolescent health awareness programs.	2.75	1.23	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Adolescent reproductive health programs receive support and participation from alumni and other community stakeholders.	2.71	1.38	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	2.93	1.29	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 38 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health under Key Result Area (KRA) 5: Building Connection. The grand mean is 2.93 and has a description of Sometimes with a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Collaborative activities with parents and stakeholders are conducted to raise awareness of adolescent reproductive health.” with a mean of 3.19, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Adolescent reproductive health programs receive support and participation from alumni and other community stakeholders.” with a mean of 2.71, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 39

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Mental Health under Key Result Area (KRA)5: Building Connection

Mental Health	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. The school collaborates with mental health professionals to organize awareness campaigns for learners, parents, and teachers.	3.29	1.30	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

2. Mental health professionals from the community regularly participate in the school's mental health support activities.	3.20	1.33	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
3. Mental health programs in the school are supported by partnerships with parents and community leaders.	3.13	1.70	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. The school engages local organizations to provide mental health workshops for learners.	3.03	1.53	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Parents and local stakeholders are involved in planning and promoting mental health initiatives in the school.	2.71	1.27	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.07	1.43	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 39 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Mental Health under Key Result Area (KRA) 5: Building Connection. The grand mean is 3.07 and has a description of Sometimes with a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “The school collaborates with mental health professionals to organize awareness campaigns for learners, parents, and teachers.” with a mean of 3.29, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Parents and local stakeholders are involved in planning and promoting mental health initiatives in the school.” with a mean of 2.71, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 40

Level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Medical, Dental, and Nursing Service under Key Result Area (KRA)5: Building Connection

Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. Community health professionals regularly participate in school health initiatives and activities for learners.	3.64	1.31	Often	Efficient

2. External facilitators are engaged efficiently to ensure the seamless execution of health programs throughout the school year.	3.50	1.28	Often	Efficient
3. Partnerships with local healthcare providers are established to enhance the delivery of medical and dental services.	3.12	1.11	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. Parents are actively informed and involved in the scheduling of health services, including dental and nursing care.	2.95	1.24	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. The school collaborates with local health organizations to provide timely deworming programs for learners.	2.91	1.44	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.22	1.28	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 40 shows the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services under Key Result Area (KRA) 5: Building Connection. The grand mean is 3.22 and has a description of Sometimes with a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “Community health professionals regularly participate in school health initiatives and activities for learners.” with a mean of 3.64, which has a description of Often and a descriptive rating of Efficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the task “The school collaborates with local health organizations to provide timely deworming programs for learners.” with a mean of 2.91, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 41

Summary of level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs under Key Result Area (KRA)5: Building Connection

Summary of KRA 5: Building Connection	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
1. WASH in Schools	3.55	1.37	Often	Efficient
2. Medical, Dental, and Nursing Services	3.22	1.28	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

3. Mental Health	3.07	1.43	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
4. National Drug Education Program	2.95	1.25	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
5. Adolescent Reproductive Health	2.93	1.29	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
6. School-Based Feeding Program	2.87	1.24	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.10	1.31	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 41 shows the summary of the level of work efficiency of the respondents in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs under Key Result Area (KRA)5: Building Connection. The grand mean is 3.10 which has a description Sometimes and a descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under WASH in Schools program with a mean score of 3.55 which has a description Often and descriptive rating of Efficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under School-Based Feeding Program with a mean score of 2.87 which has a description Sometimes and a descriptive rating Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 42

Level of Work Efficiency of the School Health Program Administrators in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs across all Key Result Areas (KRA)

Criteria	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Descriptive Rating
Leading strategically (KRA 1)	3.10	1.36	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Managing school operations and resources (KRA 2)	3.16	1.33	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Focusing on teaching and learning (KRA 3)	3.20	1.34	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Developing self and others (KRA 4)	3.17	1.37	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Building connection (KRA 5)	3.10	1.31	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient
Grand Mean	3.14	1.34	Sometimes	Neither Efficient nor Inefficient

Note: SD <1.0 = low variability, SD between 1.0 – 1.25 = moderate variability, SD >1.25 = high variability (Ernst, D., & Häcker, J., 2024)

Table 42 shows the level of work efficiency of the School Health Program Administrators in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs across all Key Result Areas (KRA). The grand mean is 3.14 and has a description of Sometimes with a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The highest level of work efficiency is observed under the criterion “Focusing on teaching and learning” with a mean of 3.20, which has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. The lowest level of work efficiency is observed under the criteria “Leading strategically” and “Building connection” both with a mean of 3.10, which have a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient.

Table 43
Relationship between the age and work efficiency of school health program administrators in the implementation of OK sa Deped Programs

Age					
Key Result Areas	Pearson's r	p-value	Level of Correlation	Interpretation	Decision
Leading strategically (KRA 1)	0.098	0.333	Weak positive correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Managing school operations and	0.204	0.042	Weak positive correlation	Statistically significant	Reject Ho

resources (KRA 2)					
Focusing on teaching and learning (KRA 3)	0.181	0.071	Weak positive correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Developing self and others (KRA 4)	0.274	0.006	Moderate positive correlation	Statistically significant	Reject Ho
Building connection (KRA 5)	0.17	0.090	Weak positive correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho

Note. * $p < .05$ (statistically significant at the 5% level, indicating reasonably strong evidence that the correlation is real), ** $p < .01$ (statistically significant at the 1% level, providing stronger evidence that the correlation is real), *** $p < .001$ (correlation is statistically significant at the 0.1% level, offering very strong evidence that the correlation is real.) (Jaadi, 2021)

Note. 0.00 to 0.10 (Negligible correlation), 0.10 to 0.39 (Weak correlation), 0.40 to 0.69 (Moderate correlation), 0.70 to 0.89 (Strong correlation), 0.90 to 1.00 (Very strong correlation) (Bhandari, 2023)

Table 43 shows the relationship between the age and work efficiency of school health program administrators in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs. It is revealed that Managing School Operations and Resources (p-value = 0.042) and Developing Self and Others (p-value = 0.006) show a significant relationship with the age of the respondents. Managing School Operations and Resources revealed a Pearson's r value of 0.204, which indicates a weak positive correlation with the age of the respondents. Furthermore, Developing Self and Others revealed a Pearson's r value of 0.274, which indicates a moderate positive correlation with the age of the respondents.

Table 44
Relationship between the gender and work efficiency of school health program administrators in the implementation of OK sa Deped Programs

Gender					
Key Result Areas	Pearson's r	p-value	Level of Correlation	Interpretation	Decision
Leading strategically (KRA 1)	-0.114	0.261	Weak negative correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Managing school operations and resources (KRA 2)	-0.069	0.494	Weak negative correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho

Focusing on teaching and learning (KRA 3)	-0.027	0.792	Weak negative correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Developing self and others (KRA 4)	-0.092	0.364	Weak negative correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Building connection (KRA 5)	-0.057	0.576	Weak negative correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho

Note. * $p < .05$ (statistically significant at the 5% level, indicating reasonably strong evidence that the correlation is real), ** $p < .01$ (statistically significant at the 1% level, providing stronger evidence that the correlation is real), *** $p < .001$ (correlation is statistically significant at the 0.1% level, offering very strong evidence that the correlation is real.) (Jaadi, 2021)

Note. 0.00 to 0.10 (Negligible correlation), 0.10 to 0.39 (Weak correlation), 0.40 to 0.69 (Moderate correlation), 0.70 to 0.89 (Strong correlation), 0.90 to 1.00 (Very strong correlation) (Bhandari, 2023)

Table 44 shows the relationship between the age and work efficiency of school health program administrators in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs. The data revealed that the gender of the respondents doesn't have a significant relationship with work efficiency.

Table 45

Relationship between the years of service and work efficiency of school health program administrators in the implementation of OK sa Deped Programs

Years of Service					
Key Result Areas	Pearson's r	p-value	Level of Correlation	Interpretation	Decision
Leading strategically (KRA 1)	-0.062	0.542	Weak negative correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Managing school operations and resources (KRA 2)	0.002	0.988	Negligible positive correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Focusing on teaching and learning (KRA 3)	-0.058	0.563	Weak negative correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Developing self and	0.009	0.927	Negligible positive correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho

others (KRA 4)

Building connection (KRA 5)	-0.089	0.379	Weak negative correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
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Note. * $p < .05$ (statistically significant at the 5% level, indicating reasonably strong evidence that the correlation is real), ** $p < .01$ (statistically significant at the 1% level, providing stronger evidence that the correlation is real), *** $p < .001$ (correlation is statistically significant at the 0.1% level, offering very strong evidence that the correlation is real.) (Jaadi, 2021)

Note. 0.00 to 0.10 (Negligible correlation), 0.10 to 0.39 (Weak correlation), 0.40 to 0.69 (Moderate correlation), 0.70 to 0.89 (Strong correlation), 0.90 to 1.00 (Very strong correlation) (Bhandari, 2023)

Table 45 shows the relationship between the years of service and work efficiency of school health program administrators in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs. The data revealed that the years of service of the respondents doesn't have a significant relationship with work efficiency.

Table 46

Relationship between the highest educational attainment and work efficiency of school health program administrators in the implementation of OK sa Deped Programs

Highest Educational Attainment					
Key Result Areas	Pearson's r	p-value	Level of Correlation	Interpretation	Decision
Leading strategically (KRA 1)	-0.134	0.184	Weak negative correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Managing school operations and resources (KRA 2)	0.185	0.065	Weak positive correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Focusing on teaching and learning (KRA 3)	-0.036	0.725	Weak negative correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Developing self and others (KRA 4)	0.046	0.652	Weak positive correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho
Building connection (KRA 5)	0.026	0.797	Weak positive correlation	Not statistically significant	Accept Ho

Note. * $p < .05$ (statistically significant at the 5% level, indicating reasonably strong evidence that the correlation is real), ** $p < .01$ (statistically significant at the 1% level, providing stronger evidence that the correlation is real), *** $p < .001$ (correlation is statistically significant at the 0.1% level, offering very strong evidence that the correlation is real.) (Jaadi, 2021)

Note. 0.00 to 0.10 (Negligible correlation), 0.10 to 0.39 (Weak correlation), 0.40 to 0.69 (Moderate correlation), 0.70 to 0.89 (Strong correlation), 0.90 to 1.00 (Very strong correlation) (Bhandari, 2023)

Table 46 shows the relationship between the highest educational attainment and work efficiency of school health program administrators in the implementation of OK sa DepEd Programs. The data revealed that the highest educational attainment of the respondents doesn't have a significant relationship with work efficiency.

Table 47
Problems encountered by the respondents in the implementation of the OK (Oplan Kalusugan) sa Department of Education programs

Problems Encountered	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Insufficient funding for program activities.	61	11.44%	1
Delays in the implementation of scheduled activities or maintenance.	60	11.26%	2
Lack of timely procurement and delivery of necessary materials.	59	11.07%	3
Inadequate training and capacity-building for staff.	54	10.13%	4
Incomplete or inaccurate data collection and reporting.	52	9.76%	5.5
Insufficient monitoring and evaluation of program effectiveness.	52	9.76%	5.5
Lack of clear policies and guidelines for program implementation.	50	9.38%	7
Poor coordination and communication with local government units (LGUs) or external partners.	49	9.19%	8.5
Ineffective utilization of available resources.	49	9.19%	8.5
Low participation and engagement from learners, parents, and other stakeholders.	47	8.82%	10
Total	533	100.00%	

Table 47 detailed the issues encountered by respondents during the implementation of the OK (*Oplan Kalusugan*) sa Department of Education programs. "Insufficient funding for program activities" rated highest, with a frequency of 61, accounting for 11.44% of all respondents. The least experienced complaint was "Low participation and engagement from learners, parents, and other stakeholders," which had a frequency of 47 and included 8.82% of respondents.

Proposed intervention measures to enhance work efficiency of school health program administrators

Table 48
Proposed Intervention Measures

Problems	Intervention Measure	Objectives	Activities	Time Frame	Person(s) Involved	Resources Needed	Expected Outcomes
1. Insufficient funding for program activities .	Increased Financial Support	Secure an additional 20% funding for program activities within the next fiscal year	Develop grant proposals, engage with government and private sector partners	Annually	Schools Division Superintendent, Division Medical Officer, local government officials, private sector partners	Financial resources, grant writing materials	20% increase in funding secured, leading to sustainable and expanded health services within one year
2. Delays in the implementation of scheduled activities or maintenance.	Timely Implementation of Activities	Reduce delays in scheduled activities by 50% within six months	Develop a detailed activity schedule, assign specific responsibilities, monitor progress regularly	Within 6 months	Division Medical Officer, School Health Unit Nurses, <i>Oplan Kalusugan</i> Flagship Program Coordinators	Scheduling tools, monitoring software	50% reduction in delays, ensuring timely implementation of activities
3. Lack of timely procurement and delivery of necessary	Efficient Procurement Processes	Ensure timely acquisition and delivery of materials within six months.	Implement a centralized procurement system, train staff on efficient	Within 6 months	Procurement officers, Division Medical Officer, School Health Unit Nurses	Procurement software, training materials	Timely procurement and delivery of necessary materials,

materials.			procurement practices				reducing delays
4. Inadequate training and capacity-building for staff.	Enhanced Training Programs	Improve staff training and capacity-building by 90% within one year	Conduct workshops and seminars on relevant topics, provide ongoing training opportunities	Quarterly	Division Medical Officer, School Health Unit Nurses, <i>Oplan Kalusugan</i> Flagship Program Coordinators	Training materials, budget for trainers, venue	90% of staff demonstrate improved skills and knowledge within one year
5. Incomplete or inaccurate data collection and reporting.	Accurate Data Collection and Reporting	Achieve 100% accuracy in data collection and reporting within one year	Create consistent data gathering tools, and teach employees on proper data entry and reporting.	Within 1 year	Division Medical Officer, M&E specialists, School Health Unit Nurses	Data collection tools, training materials	100% accuracy in data collection and reporting, improving program evaluation
6. Insufficient monitoring and evaluation of program effectiveness.	Comprehensive Monitoring and Evaluation	Implement a robust M&E framework within one year, with 100% staff trained	Develop and implement M&E framework, train staff on data collection and analysis	Within 1 year	Division Medical Officer, M&E specialists, School Health Unit Nurses	Monitoring tools, training materials	Effective program evaluation and continuous improvement

7. Lack of clear policies and guidelines for program implementation.	Clear Policies and Guidelines	Formulate and disseminate clear policies and guidelines within one year, with 100% compliance	Develop policies, provide training on policy implementation	Within 1 year	Schools Division Superintendent, Division Medical Officer, policymakers	Policy documents, training materials	100% compliance with new policies, improving program execution
8. Poor coordination and communication with local government units (LGUs) or external partners	Improved Coordination and Communication	Establish regular communication channels with 100% of LGUs and external partners within six months	Schedule regular meetings, create joint action plans	Monthly	Division Medical Officer, Program Coordinators, local government officials, external partners	Meeting venues, communication tools	Improved coordination and collaboration with stakeholders
9. Ineffective utilization of available resources.	Effective Utilization of Resources	Optimize resource utilization by 50% within one year	Conduct resource audits, implement resource management strategies	Within 1 year	Division Medical Officer, School Health Unit Nurses, Program Coordinators	Resource management tools, training materials	50% improvement in resource utilization, enhancing program efficiency
10. Low participation and engagement	Increased Stakeholder Engagement	Boost participation and engagement from	Organize community engagement activities	All year round	Division Medical Officer, School Health Unit	Engagement materials, budget	50% increase in stakeholder participation

from learners, parents, and other stakeholders.		learners, parents, and stakeholders by 50% within one year	, conduct awareness campaigns		Nurses, Program Coordinators	for events	tion and engagement, improving program outcomes
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These proposed intervention measures aim to address the identified challenges and enhance the overall work efficiency of school health administrators in the Schools Division of Tarlac Province. By implementing these specific, measurable, attainable, realistic, and time-bound (SMART) objectives, the administrators can achieve higher performance levels and contribute to the successful implementation of health programs.

DISCUSSION

1. Level of Work Efficiency of the Respondents

Leading Strategically

The overall work efficiency in implementing OK sa DepEd programs under Leading Strategically is rated as Neither Efficient nor Inefficient, indicating average time management and task completion with occasional delays. The School-Based Feeding Program and National Drug Education Program showed higher efficiency due to their documented benefits on health, education outcomes, attendance, and cost-efficiency (Wang & Fawzi, 2020; Gelli et al., 2021). The National Drug Education Program's structured approach and impact on reducing substance use also enhance its efficiency (Caulkins et al., 2022). Moreover, the WASH in Schools program faces logistical challenges, limited staff capacity, and inadequate funding, resulting in lower efficiency (Graham et al., 2015; UNICEF & WHO, 2016). Effective strategic leadership, as noted by Carvalho et al. (2021) and Smith (2024), requires proper resource management, continuous training, and clear policies to improve program outcomes.

Managing School Operations and Resources

The overall work efficiency in implementing OK sa DepEd programs is rated as Neither Efficient nor Inefficient, indicating average time management and task completion with occasional delays. Recent studies highlighted significant challenges such as insufficient funding, delays in scheduled activities, and lack of timely procurement and delivery of materials (Walters et al., 2022). These issues hinder efficient management, leading to average performance. Additionally, inadequate training, incomplete data collection, and reporting contribute to inefficiencies (Levinson et al., 2019). The rating of Sometimes reflects inconsistent task completion and satisfactory outcomes, attributed to

problems like insufficient monitoring, lack of clear policies, and poor coordination with local government units (LGUs) or external partners (National Academies Press, 2020). Addressing these issues through improved policymaking and resource allocation could enhance the overall efficiency of SHPAs.

Focusing on Teaching and Learning

In this KRA, the level of work efficiency of the SHPAs also has a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. This rating indicates that the administrators' time management and task completion are average, with occasional delays or missed deadlines. Moreover, Webster et al. (2020) found that administrators' involvement in health promotion programs significantly impacts the overall school environment, which in turn supports teaching and learning by creating a healthier, more focused student body. Similarly, Levinson et al. (2019) emphasized that effective school health services contribute to better student health, directly linked to improved academic performance and classroom behavior. These findings underscore the critical role of administrators in integrating health programs with educational goals to enhance overall school efficiency and student success.

Developing Self and Others

The level of work efficiency of the SHPAs in this KRA also revealed a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. This rating indicates that administrators' time management and task completion are average, with occasional delays or missed deadlines. Studies support the findings on the work efficiency of SHPAs in this KRA. Levinson et al. (2019) found that school health services face challenges due to inconsistent implementation and lack of comprehensive interventions, impacting administrators' ability to manage time and tasks effectively. Additionally, Pricellas et al. (2016) emphasized that while school administrators possess strong leadership skills, their effectiveness in developing others is sometimes hindered by inadequate support and resources, leading to average efficiency and occasional delays.

Building Connections

Lastly, the same goes under this KRA, where results also revealed a description of Sometimes and a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient. This rating indicates that the administrators' time management and task completion are average, with occasional delays or missed deadlines. These results align with the findings of Price et al. (2018), who found that school administrators often face challenges in effectively managing time and tasks due to inconsistent support and resources, which impacts their ability to build strong connections within the school community. Moreover, Smith et al. (2021) emphasized that while administrators play a crucial role in fostering a supportive school environment, their efficiency is often hindered by limited professional development opportunities and inadequate collaboration with staff, leading to average performance and

occasional delays. These studies highlight the need for enhanced support systems to improve administrators' efficiency in building connections within the school environment.

2. Relationship between the demographic profile and work efficiency of school health program administrators

The findings revealed that age had a significant positive impact on managing school operations and resources, as well as on developing self and others, but it did not significantly affect other areas like strategic leadership and building connections. Gender was found to have no significant impact on work efficiency across all KRAs, and similarly, years of service did not show a significant influence on any of the KRAs. Educational attainment also did not significantly impact work efficiency across the different areas. The findings aligned with what Leeman et al. (2018) discovered in their study: demographic factors such as age and educational attainment have limited influence on the effectiveness of school health program implementation. This aligns with the study's conclusion that these factors do not significantly affect administrators' performance across various KRAs. Moreover, the study by Smith et al. (2021) highlighted that while demographic factors like gender and years of service are often considered in administrative roles, they do not significantly impact the efficiency of task completion and time management. Therefore, this study concluded that demographic factors do not significantly affect the work efficiency of school health program administrators, with only a few instances showing significant correlations that were not sufficient to reject the null hypothesis.

Conclusions

Based on the results of thorough analysis on the demographic profile, level of work efficiency of the school health program administrators, and the problems encountered in the implementation of *Oplan Kalusugan* in the Schools Division of Tarlac Province, the following conclusion was drawn.

The overall level of work efficiency of school health program administrators in the implementation of *Oplan Kalusugan* in the Schools Division of Tarlac Province has a descriptive rating of Neither Efficient nor Inefficient, with a description of Sometimes. This indicates that administrators' time management and task completion are average, with occasional delays or missed deadlines. Significant relationships were observed in specific areas: age positively impacted managing school operations and resources, as well as developing self and others, but did not significantly affect strategic leadership and building connections. Gender, years of service, and educational attainment did not significantly influence work efficiency across any key result areas (KRAs). The study concludes that demographic factors do not significantly affect the work efficiency of school health program administrators, with only a few instances showing significant correlations that were insufficient to reject the null hypothesis.

Recommendations

After a thorough analysis of the research findings, the researcher has drawn the following recommendations:

1. The Department of Education should implement targeted training programs prior to the beginning of the academic year 2025-2026 to improve strategic leadership, operational management, teaching methodologies, professional development, and stakeholder collaboration among School Health Program Administrators (SHPAs). Financial support for health programs should also be increased and sustained to ensure successful implementation.
2. The Schools Division of Tarlac Province should establish a rigorous selection process for SHPAs prior to the beginning of the academic year 2026-2027, considering experience and educational qualifications. Ongoing professional development opportunities should be provided to enhance administrators' skills, improving program implementation.
3. The division school health unit should streamline procurement processes and improve data collection and reporting systems by December 2025. Enhanced monitoring and evaluation mechanisms should be implemented to assess program performance and inform continuous improvement.
4. SHPAs should identify areas for improvement in their work efficiency and develop strategies to address these gaps by March 2026. Best practices should be shared, participation in professional development programs should be encouraged, and coordination and communication with local government units and external partners should be improved.
5. The school health system should be made more responsive and efficient by June 2026, directly benefiting students' well-being and academic achievement. Regular communication and involvement in decision-making processes will increase participation and support from students and other stakeholders.
6. Policymakers should use this study's findings prior to the beginning of the academic year 2025-2026 to develop targeted interventions aimed at improving SHPAs' work efficiency. This will include professional development programs, enhanced support systems, and policies addressing specific needs and challenges identified in the study.
7. Future researchers should consider the limitations identified in this study and strive to address them in their research designs. This includes using mixed-methods approaches, longitudinal studies, and expanding the range of variables examined. Future studies should aim to include larger and more diverse samples to enhance the generalizability of their findings. Researchers should also explore the impact of organizational culture and personal motivation on work efficiency to provide a more holistic understanding of the factors influencing the performance of SHPAs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Informed Consent

The researcher ensured that participants understood the study, their roles, and their rights, and this fostered trust and accurate data collection.

Confidentiality

The participants' identities and personal information were protected by assigning unique codes to each respondent and storing data securely, and this prevented any direct link between the data and the participants' identities, safeguarding them from professional and personal repercussions.

Data Management

The researcher handled data responsibly to maintain credibility and prevent misuse of inaccuracies, and data was stored in encrypted files, and access was restricted to authorized personnel only.

Fair Treatment

All participants were treated equally, regardless of age, gender, ethnicity, or other factors, and this ensured fairness throughout the study. The sample was selected without bias, and the study methodologies were applied consistently to ensure fairness and representativeness.

Reciprocity

A reciprocal relationship was maintained by valuing participants' contributions and ensuring their safety and respect throughout the study. Participants were kept informed about the study's progress and outcomes, fostering a sense of collaboration and mutual benefit.

Data Destruction

After the study concluded, all data was securely deleted to protect participants' privacy. This involved permanently erasing digital files and shredding physical documents, preventing any unauthorized access or misuse of the data.

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